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Long term stability of a Mn-rich pre-coated AISI 441 for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Interconnects at 650 °C in air

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Abstract

Sandvik Materials Technology develops nanocoatings for Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) stainless steel interconnects. The properties of an AISI 441 steel grade coated with cerium and cobalt have been studied extensively. It has been shown that the material forms a stable and protective $(\text{Co},\text{Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ spinel phase over time. However, the trend in SOFC have been to decrease working temperatures from above 800°C and today commercial systems are sold that operate below 650°C. At those low temperatures the diffusion of Mn from the AISI 441 steel is much slower and therefore the formation of the $(\text{Co},\text{Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ spinel phase is not observed. In this work, we have developed a new coating where Mn and Co have been incorporated to the metal coating in order to enhance the formation of the desired spinel. The results are compared with the standard coating with Ce and Co as coating composition. The interconnect materials were exposed at different oxidation times at 650 °C and they were characterized by means of electron microscopy techniques (SEM and EDX) and contact resistance measurements (ASR). The development of the surface oxides as well as the influence of these oxides on the performance of the material is evaluated. A stable $(\text{Co},\text{Mn})_3\text{O}_4$ spinel phase is formed after more than 10kh of exposure. However, similar Cr_2O_3 scale thickness is observed as for the standard coating, and therefore no change in the contact resistance was observed, highlighting the good performance of the standard coating as well at low temperatures as 650 °C.

1. Introduction

Sandvik Surface Technology is a production unit within AB Sandvik Materials Technology (SMT). SMT belongs to the Sandvik group and is a world-leading manufacturer of advanced stainless steels and special alloys for the most demanding industries. Sandvik Surface Technology offers a portfolio of cost effective coated steel strip for electronics applications, interconnects for Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFC) and bipolar plates for Polymer Electrolyte Fuel Cells (PEM).

The roll-to-roll coating lines for mass production provides an outstanding opportunity for the cost-effective and industrial mass production of SOFC interconnects and PEM bipolar plates. The pre-coated solution reduces some of the handling that comes with batch coating of individual plates. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the coating line developed in Sandviken (Sweden). Coils of any steel grade according to customer specifications with a width smaller than 800 mm and a thickness between 0.07 and 0.8 mm can be introduced in the coating line. Before entering the coating line the coils are cleaned by a wet chemical de-greasing process, followed by surface inspection. This process is followed by an in-line plasma cleaning/etching. In the next process the metal layers are deposited on the coil by Sandvik's continuous PVD coating process. The coating thickness and uniformity is monitored with an

X-ray inspection system. Before shipping, the coils are going through testing, slitting and packaging processes according to customer specifications.

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Figure 1. Schematics of the roll to roll coating line developed for Sandvik Surface Technology in Sandviken (Sweden). The figure shows the different steps that the material undergoes during the coating process: (1) Cleaning and inspection; (2) Coating by Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) methods; (3) In-line inspection by X-Ray techniques; (4) Final testing, slitting and packing.

Sandvik Sanergy™ HT 441 has been shown to be an excellent material to be used as SOFC interconnects [1-3]. This product is an AISI 441 steel grade coated with cerium and cobalt. At high temperature, i.e. > 800 °C, the material has shown to form a double layer oxide scale with an inner Cr₂O₃ scale and an outer spinel layer. The inner Cr₂O₃ scale typically have poor electrical conductivity and its thickness sets the contact resistance. The outer protective spinel layer have typically a (Co,Mn)₃O₄ composition and is formed by diffusion of Mn from the steel over time. This spinel phase is well known to improve the properties of the interconnect material due to the higher electronic conductivity than the (Cr,Mn)₃O₄ spinel that is formed on the uncoated materials [3]. In addition, this (Co,Mn)₃O₄ spinel has the capability to reduce the Cr vaporization with almost one order of magnitude [4]. The volatile Cr species may otherwise lead to cathode poisoning and therefore, dramatic loss of performance in the SOFC stack.

In the effort to reduce the operation temperature of SOFC, Sandvik Sanergy™ HT 441 has been studied at 650 °C. Recent studies [4] have shown that Sandvik Sanergy™ HT 441 forms a stable and dense Co₃O₄ spinel after 500 h of exposure in air at 650 °C. The material also showed low Cr vaporization rates as well as good contact resistance values due to the thin Cr₂O₃ layer that formed at these temperatures. Falk Windisch et al. [4] made a comparison with an AISI 441 steel grade coated with a much thicker (15-20 μm) (Co,Mn)₃O₄ ceramic coating. In that study both the PVD and the ceramic coating showed good performance in terms of Cr vaporization and contact resistance. However, concern was raised regarding any additional heat treatment that may be necessary to densify certain

ceramic based coatings. Such heat treatment is typically performed at high temperatures during which the Cr_2O_3 scale may grow relatively thick, which would increase the ASR. In this work PVD coatings on AISI 441 steel grades of both Ce+Co and Ce+Co/Mn coatings are produced in order to evaluate their properties after exposure at 650 °C.

2. Experiments

Sheets of cold rolled commercial grade ferritic stainless steel AISI 441 (EN 1.4509) were used in the present study. The nominal chemical composition of the steel was (wt%): 18 Cr, 0.11 Ti, 0.47 Nb, 0.28 Mn, 0.54 Si, 0.012 C, Ni 0.13. The thickness of the sheets was 0.2 mm. Two different coatings were applied on both side of the steel sheets: (1) 600 nm cobalt and 20 nm cerium (cerium as coating layer 1) and (2) 600 nm Cobalt + Manganese (Co:Mn 1:1) and 20 nm cerium (cerium as coating layer 1). All the coatings were deposited in a PVD batch coater. Before coating, the substrates were cleaned in an alkali detergent at 60 °C for 10 min. After the alkaline cleaning the substrates were rinsed in hot tap water, deionized water and finally in ethanol.

The coated substrate sheets were cut in coupons of a size of 30 mm x 40 mm, and pierced with a hole with a diameter of 3 mm used for hanging the samples during high temperature cyclic oxidation in ambient air. The coupons were oxidized in a muffle furnace and during the oxidation experiments the coupons were hanging on a platinum thread to avoid contact with other coupons and to expose the same surface area. Three coupons of each coating type were oxidized at 650 °C for 13000 hours corresponding to one year and a half of exposure.

Microstructure and chemical composition of the oxide scales were analyzed in an FEI Quanta 200 FEG Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) equipped with an Oxford Instruments X-MaxN Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) detector and INCAEnergy software. Cross sections were prepared by using a Leica TI3X Broad Ion Beam (BIB). A low speed saw with diamond blade was used to cut the sample in half to enable BIB cross sections from the center of the sample and not from the edges.

Electrical scale resistance measurements (ASR measurements) were carried out on samples that had been isothermally exposed for 13000 h at 650 °C before the electrodes were contacted and the ASR measurement was carried out. Pt was used as electrode material for these ASR measurements. A sputter mask of 1 x 1 cm² was placed on the pre-oxidized samples and a very thin layer of Pt was sputtered on top of the oxide scale. After the sputtering step, the sputtered area was painted with Pt paste. These samples were then dried for 10 min at 150 °C followed by a Pt sintering step for 1 h at 650 °C. To measure the ASR value, a Probostat (NorECs, Norway) test cell, placed in a tubular furnace was used to connect the sample to Solartron 1260A impedance analyzer.

3. Results and discussions

Figure 2 shows cross-section SEM images of the coated materials after 13000 h of exposure in air at 650 °C. Both materials form dense oxide layers of slightly different thicknesses and different compositions as it can be expected by the nominal composition. From the EDX line scans it can be observed that after this time of exposure (> 1.5 years) the Ce+Co/Mn coating forms a $\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{Co}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ spinel oxide layer while the Ce+Co leads to a Co_3O_4 spinel oxide formation. The EDX line scan measurements also show that both coatings form fairly thin Cr_2O_3 layers of similar thicknesses (~ 350-400 nm). Only a slight difference in density is observed in both coatings. It is likely that a thin crust above the pores of the Ce+Co/Mn coated material has been lost as some remnants can be observed on the right part of the

coating. This would explain the difference of thickness that it can be observed between both coatings and the higher densification of the Mn containing coated material.

Figure 2. SEM images of cross sections BIB samples and the corresponding EDX lines scans (blue arrow) of the Ce+Co/Mn and the Ce+Co coated material on AISI 441 steel grade after 13000 h of exposure in air at 650 °C.

Figure 3 shows ASR measurements in function of temperature carried out in air for both materials after exposure at 650 °C for 13000 h. It can be observed that both materials have a semiconducting behavior. Both coatings show very good contact resistance values with ASR values below 30 mΩcm² at 650 °C. These values at 650 °C and such long exposure times are the lowest ASR values reported in the literature so far on this type of experiments to the best of our knowledge.

Figure 3. Area Specific Resistance (ASR) measurements in function of temperature in air after 13000 h of exposure at 650 °C for the Ce+Co/Mn and the Ce+Co coatings.

At high temperatures, i.e. > 800 °C, Sanergy HT™ 441 leads to the formation of a (Co,Mn)₃O₄ spinel layer as a result of the Mn diffusion from the steel [5]. At lower temperatures, the composition of the spinel is different due to the lower diffusion of Mn at those temperatures. As it can be seen from the EDX line scan in Fig. 2 that even after more than 13000 h of exposure at 650 °C hardly any Mn has diffused from the steel into the spinel on the Ce+Co coated sample. This is also confirmed by the image of the Ce+Co/Mn coating where it can be observed that the stoichiometry of Co:Mn remains 1:1 as the nominal composition.

It has been shown that the main contribution to the ASR on these chromia forming steel materials is the poorly conducting Cr₂O₃ layer that forms beneath the spinel layer. In a recent study by Goebel et al. [6] samples with different Co spinel thickness were evaluated and it was shown that the contribution to the ASR from the formed Co spinel was negligible compared with the contribution from the Cr₂O₃ layer. Figure 2 shows similar Cr₂O₃ thickness for both materials. This is translated to similar performance in ASR, which can also be seen in Figure 3. So although the (Co,Mn)₃O₄ spinel has a higher conductivity than Co₃O₄ [7], the contribution from the spinel to the ASR in the interconnect is so little that incorporating Mn into the standard Ce+Co coating is not considered necessary.

4. Conclusions

A new Ce+Co/Mn metal coating was produced by PVD methods at Sandvik Surface Technology and compared with the standard Sandvik Sanergy HT™ 441 coating (Ce+Co). Both materials were exposed at 650 °C for more than 13000 h and characterized by means of SEM and ASR measurements. Both materials show the formation of homogenous and dense coatings of different compositions: Mn_{1.5}Co_{1.5}O₄ spinel for the Co/Mn coating and Co₃O₄ spinel for the standard coatings. Likewise, thin Cr₂O₃ layers were measured from the SEM images. This leads to similar performance on the ASR measurements. It can be concluded that the standard Ce+Co coated AISI 441 steel forms thin Cr₂O₃ layers when exposed to low temperatures (650 °C) and show overall good performance and therefore no addition of Mn to the coating should be necessary.

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References

- [1] J. Froitzheim, S. Canovic, M. Nikumaa, R. Sachitanand, L.G. Johansson and J. E. Svensson *J. of Power Sources*, 220, 217 (2012).
- [2] J.G. Grolig, J. Froitzheim, J.E. Svensson, *J. of Power Sources*, 248 1007 (2014)
- [3] H. Falk-Windisch, J. Claquesin, M. Sattari, J.-E. Svensson, J. Froitzheim, *J. of Power Sources*, 343 1 (2017).
- [4] H. Falk-Windisch, J.-E. Svensson, J. Froitzheim. *ECS Transactions*, 78 (1) 1607-1614 (2017).
- [5] M. Stanislawski, J. Froitzheim, L. Niewolak, W. J. Quadackers, K. Hilpert, T. Markus and L. Singheiser, *J. Power Sources*, 164, 578 (2007).

- [6] C. Goebel, A. G. Fefekos, J.-E. Svensson, J. Froitzheim. *J. of Power Sources*, 383 110 (2018).
- [7] A. Petric, H. Ling. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 90 (5) 1515 (2007).